

In An Era of New Media Technologies: Librarians and the Fight Against Information Misuse

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi

Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria
ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972
onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com
+2348037237792

ABSTRACT

We are in era which has been transformed by the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) with information growing exponentially. This transformation further made information dissemination and accessibility very easy more so through the new media technologies. New media technologies often referred to as Web 2.0- encompass a wide variety of web-related communication technologies, such as blogs, wikis, online social networking, virtual worlds and other social media forms. This study therefore is a survey on the roles of librarians in the fight against Information Misuse in this Period of new media technologies with special reference to Nigeria. The study applied descriptive design with a sampled population of 420 librarians purposively selected among registered librarians in Nigeria. A modified Likert scale four point structured questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collections while mode and percentage were used to analyze the data collected and presented in tables. The study discovered among other things that politicians and individual social media users are most culpable of information misuse in Nigeria while new media such as Twitter; Instagram, Whatsapp and Facebook Messenger are being used to peddle misinformation with enormous negative effects on the society, It was further ascertained that librarians as information managers have prominent role to play in the fight against this anti-societal activity in Nigeria and by extension the world.

Keywords: Technology, Information, Information Misuse, Society, Librarians, New Media, Society

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology which is the application of scientific knowledge in production has transformed the ways we do most things. In the area of information accessibility and dissemination, the arrow head is information and communication technology (ICT) which spearheaded the emergence of what we today know as new media technologies where access to and distribution of information have become very easy. As has been observed, information which in its real state is the communication of news and knowledge and that which helps to reduce uncertainty and assist us in decision making (Onwubiko,2016), has become the greatest asset of any nation and the first among all factors of production. This is because a well informed society stands out in the mist of others as it stands ahead in development. On the other hand, information like fire may also turn a bad servant and consume the society if not appropriately applied. Stating the obvious, to many people, Information means many things that it may be compare with the story of the seven blind men and the elephant depending on the context and for this reason, depending on the understanding and intent, it may be applied to achieve good, bad or the ugly. As explained by deWatteville and Gilbert (2000), information is any potentially useful fact, quantity or value that can be expressed uniquely with exactness. While in the

views of Womboh and Abba (2008) it is processed data that aids decision making. It could also be visualized as a commodity that could be bought or sold. In this study, information is anything that we come in contact with directly or indirectly that adds to our knowledge and is capable of causing a human mind to change its opinion about the current state of the real world, and in a library, information is data that have been processed into form that is meaningful to the recipient/user and is of real or perceived value in current and future decision.

Suffice it to say, that we are in era which has been transformed by the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) with information growing exponentially. . This transformation further made information dissemination and accessibility very easy more so through the new media technologies. New media technologies often referred to as Web 2.0- encompass a wide variety of web-related communication technologies, such as blogs, wikis, online social networking, virtual worlds and other social media forms (Friedman & Friedman, 2008). The new media unlike the old media (television, newspapers, magazines, radio, etc) are flexible channels for content creation and dissemination.. Availability and accessibility of these pieces of information has given rise to a wave of concern, if not a threat to the continued existence of the society around the globe. This quantum of information at the finger tips of the public has been misused for many reasons, but particularly for self interest.

Information misuse connotes the unethical use of information usually with the intention to manipulate, mislead or cause harm to an individual, group or an organisation. It is an intentional or deliberate distortion or misrepresentation of a factual content with the aim of achieving predetermined outcome. Santos-D'amorim and Miranda (2021) associated misused concepts of misinformation, disinformation and mal-information to words such as; bias, propaganda, retracted papers, conspiracy theories, misleading representation in maps, charts and graphics, fake news, click bait, hoax, satire or parody, imposter website, fake reviews, phishing, filter bubbles, and echo chambers. In the last few years, false and misleading information has caused or contributed to a wide range of harm to individuals and groups across the world and Nigeria in particular. For instance, in recent years in Nigeria misinformation and propaganda did spearhead the agitation for freedom by both the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) of the Southeast, Nigeria and the Oduduwas of the Southwest, Nigeria among others. There was also the issue of October, 2020 Has tag ENDSARS and Islamic Movement of Nigeria (IMN) saga in which hundreds of youths were killed in Lagos and other parts of the country and the 2023 Presidential elections that nearly plunged the nation into ethnical and religious war, to mention but a few. Information which is originally meant to enlighten and to dispel ignorance leading to well mannered and well behaved society has been bastardized and now being used as a weapon of mass destruction in our society (Cunliffe-Jones, et al. 2021).

Be that as it may, on the face of unrelated peddling of fake news in our society, it is difficult for the public to filter, refine and select what they receive (Santin & Pra, 2021). The ability of the populace to

filter through the ubiquitous generated content which comes in form of text, pictures, graphics, videos and the likes is equally as important as the quality of decision they will make.

Information as a product is the oil that lubricates the joints that keeps modern society working and the growth therein. However, it must be used rightly. By misrepresenting reality with traces of truth, there is a distortion of entire collective imaginary and manipulation of public opinion which in turn leads to major problems politically, socially and economically (Satin & Pra, 2021). Evidence has shown that the situation of information misuse especially in Nigeria has worsened as a result of contemporary new media. In fact the assertion is that information misuse has gained prominence through social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Google, YouTube, and other social media platforms.

New media presents a very different reality than our everyday, face-to-face reality. In the new dispensation, librarians are envisaged as gateway and guide to information. To this Akintunde (2004) explains that librarians from the foregoing have imbibed a new paradigm of service. There has been shift from being documentalist and archivist, to being a gateway to information. The librarian has also shifted from being the all knowing 'custodian' of knowledge to a 'guide' by the side. He explains that the librarian guides clients on how to navigate effectively through the wide world web (www), creates portals for his clients because of the mesh of data now readily available. Against this backdrop, the researcher felt that there is need for a social institution like the library and professionals who are effective in managing information (Librarians) to come to the rescue. This is built on the assertion that the exponential growth of information fuelled by the exploitation of media such as the web and social networking, demands that there be a mediator with the skills and capacity to extract trusted and authentic information. Such an intermediary also has to be able to deliver reliable and authoritative information to the information-seeking community as well as the new knowledge and information that has been created in recent times (Tise ,2011),.

This study therefore is an enquiry aimed at establishing the expected duties of librarians in the fight against this societal menace called information misuse in an era of new media in Nigeria as well as creating that awareness of the danger of information misuse and make recommendations where necessary. So, the primary objective of this study is to establish the duties of librarian in fighting information misuse in this period of new media technologies while other objectives include:

1. To identify those are involved in information misuse
2. To establish the new media that are used to peddle misinformation
3. To discover the consequences of information misuse to the society
4. To ascertain the duties of Librarians in the fight against information misuse

To realize the above objectives, the study was guided by five research questions.

1. Who are those involved in information misuse?
2. What new media are used to peddle misinformation?
3. What are the Consequences of information misuse to the society?
4. What duties are Librarians expected to perform in the fight against information misuse?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

As has been noted, information misuse is all about the inappropriate use of information as when initially collected. Basically, it's when data is not used the way it's initially intended to be used (Sai Chavali, 2018). It is evident as a growing issue for concern in this era of new media technology which transfers information via digital techniques, computerized systems or data networks. First established in the 20th century, this technology is most readily associated with information transfers meant to be manipulated in some way. Most forms are interactive and contain compressed data designed to be accessed in a variety of markets (Chavis, 2023). To this end, people easily believe what they read and listen to in various media channels. Digital platforms of most relevance to the globe includes website such as Google and Yahoo; open social media and micro-blogging sites such as Facebook and Tweeter; shared news websites such as Reddit; photo sharing sites such as Instagram and Snapchat; video sharing sites such as YouTube and close messaging applications such WhatsApp and Facebook Messenger (Johns, 2019). They are veritable social and political tools.

For instance in the Nigerian 2023 general elections, the new media was optimally utilized especially to disseminate or receive information concerning the elections. On the other hand, many politicians and other people used those platforms to spread information that lead to crises that resulted to loss of lives and wanton destruction of property which would have if not by the grace of God truncated the continued existence of a democracy in Nigeria. Misguided utterances through those platforms sparked ethnic and tribal chauvinism. Same digital platforms were used to promote religious hegemony by the clergy of the various religious groups in the country. Worse still; the electoral umpire in the country the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) who also utilized the same platforms assuring Nigerians of free and fair elections (International Crisis Group, 2023). However, the outcome of the elections was flawed by not keeping to the terms of the electoral Act, in which case INEC failed to upload the presidential election results electronically as promised and this did not go down well with Nigerians as it sparked media outrage.

In fact, information misuse is a wind that blows no one any good. In the first instance, it leads to erosion of trust among the people. When people are constantly exposed to misinformation or disinformation, they become skeptical about the information emanating from their leaders. Using Nigeria as a case in point since 1999, Nigerian politicians have been recycling political agenda to the point that an ordinary Nigerian knows exactly what the politicians would promise in the next political campaigns and this has resulted to the citizenry not have any atom of trust on them..

Besides, information misuse has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public; weaken democratic established institutions, polarize the society, suppression of minority groups in the country's freedom of expression would be threatened with continued misinformation and inhibit policy-making.

Inasmuch as rights and powers mean access to data. In the contrary, sometimes for instance, when an employee feels a lack of control, they can use the data they've been given access to for their own benefit. This misuse can threaten an organization's data security or even lead to a data breach. Data

misuse was in the top seven categories of threat actions in 2020 according to the Verizon 2021 Data Breach Investigations Report (DBIR). For organizations, data misuse may lead to costly lawsuits and loss of reputation.

The Research Institute of the Nationwide Children's Hospital in Columbus, Ohio, experienced a trade secrets leak that came to light in spring 2021. A researcher at the institute, together with his wife, sold the hospital's trade secrets to China. During ten years of research, the pair collected data in separate laboratories and then illegally handed it to competitors. The secret data, related to exosomes, is important for research, as well as for identifying and treating various diseases (ABC News, 2021). For conspiring and selling trade secrets, Yu Zhou, the researcher, was sentenced to 33 months in prison along with confiscation of assets and a \$2.6 million fine.

Cincinnati experienced an abuse of data in February 2020, when sensitive information was misused by a group of employees. They leaked social security and account numbers, driver's licenses, address information, and even customers' mothers' maiden names. As part of a **fraud ring**, the employees presumably wanted to set up credit accounts outside of Cincinnati, where fraudulent charges would be difficult to catch until reported to credit reporting agencies. After the incident, employees that abused their access to the bank's assets were put under criminal investigation. In turn, the bank took steps to strengthen the security of customers' accounts (Cincinnati, 2020).

For instance In February 2022 revealed Reuter (2022) Credit Suisse suffered an insider attack carried out by an employee whistleblower. The employee leaked data to which he had access to a German newspaper. As a result, information on more than 18,000 accounts (which contained more than \$100 billion) was revealed to the Süddeutsche Zeitung newspaper, and afterwards to a wide number of other global media and organizations. Journalists quickly spread the information, as it contained data on "dirty billings" belonging to some people under sanctions. Shares of Credit Suisse lost around 3% after the incident.

Likewise, on June 26, 2020, a U.S. District Court found Chinese citizen Hao Zhang guilty of trade secrets theft and economic espionage against both Avago and Skyworks. According to the court, Hao collected materials for five years with the aim of helping the Chinese government and opening his own business. Hao and his accomplices obtained information regarding the manufacturing and performance of wireless devices. The conspirators then opened their own company and tried to compete with the firms from which they stole data. Employees of the Chinese Tianjin University also took part in the scheme. (US Ministry of Justice, 2020)

While data misuse can remain unnoticeable for a long time, its consequences can bring lots of harm to an organization individuals and the society at large. In Nigeria for instance, the twists and turns of politics torch on religious, tribal and cultural believes of the people, especially in Nigeria. Exploring such avenues, politicians and their supporters use religion and tribal sentiments to stir up violence around the country.. Although violence has always been part of the electioneering in this part of the

globe, this time around it towed the tribal and religious dimension fueled by information misuse. To this end, it is very important for people to think critically, verify carefully and be careful about the information they consume or use in order to ameliorate the spread of information misuse.

As has been noted, powerful new technology makes the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplify falsehood peddled by states, populist politicians and dishonest corporate entities as they are shared by uncritical publics (Ireton & Posetti, 2018). This is in line with Butcher (2019) who affirmed that online disinformation is deliberately false or misleading material, often masquerading as news content, which is designed to attract attention and exert influence through online channels.

Contributing on the pros and cons of new media, Curran and Seaton (2003), posit that two perspectives dominate the debate about the new media in Britain: the neophilic perspective and the cultural pessimist perspective. As explained, they each have opposing views on new media and its advantages and disadvantages. The Neophiliacs or cultural optimists argue that new media is advantageous to society for several reasons. These include: enhancement of access to information and easy to access a wide range of information on practically every topic, from everyday issues to academic research. People can find information online regardless of their location and often for free, meaning new media is a very valuable resource. New networks and connections through which the global internet makes it easier for individuals to make connections that wouldn't be possible at the **local** level or through traditional (old) media. Social media also make it easier than ever for people to stay in contact with their loved ones anywhere in the world, not just through messaging but by video calling, playing games together, etc and the revitalizing of democracy that the internet has now become a source of political education and information. This can encourage citizens to play an active role in democratic societies and can make politicians more accountable to the public.

Furthermore, new media has led to cultural globalization in that we can now interact with others on a global level and form connections virtually, rather than locally. These wider networks enable 'collective intelligence' in that they allow people to share and combine resources, data, skills, and information for any given purpose. New media presents a very different reality than our everyday, face-to-face reality - a virtual environment constructed with computer graphics and digital video. Simulations surpass the virtual nature of new media and create an immersive, artificial "life". This is most obvious in computer games which provide opportunities for users to experience a "virtual life" that is simulated through digital (StudySmarter, 2023)

On the other hand, the cultural pessimists believe that the revolution in new media technologies has been exaggerated by neophiliacs and argued among other things that what is primarily new about new media is its speed the commercialization of the internet has caused considerable privacy concerns. Many companies that sell products and services on the internet now also sell their customers' data by engaging in consumer surveillance and that new digital technologies, for instance, in the form of cookies, can track and monitor data generated by users to further target potential

audiences, thereby enhancing the company's profits (Comford and Robins, 1999; Hill and Hughes, 1998 ; Curran, 2002). According to Andrew (2007), the democratized nature of the internet can harm the quality of media content. For instance, Wikipedia, a public-produced website, can sometimes be filled with poorly written, uninformed, or false information.

On the roles of libraries and librarians in curbing information misappropriation or misuse, the obvious, is that the exponential growth of information fuelled by the exploitation of media such as the web and social networking, demands that there be a mediator with the skills and capacity to extract trusted and authentic information. Such an intermediary also has to be able to deliver reliable and authoritative information to the information-seeking community as well as the new knowledge and information that has been created in recent times (Tise, 2011). It is this new knowledge and information that help to stimulate the growth and development of societies and the world. Libraries as primary gateways to information are therefore important vehicles for the acquisition of knowledge. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities and socio-economic groups regardless of their information/knowledge needs (Onwubiko, 2020)

While Nwajiuba (2019), in the context of the African Union (AU) Agenda 2063 and the Charter for African Cultural Renaissance at the 3rd Ministerial Roundtable on Information Access declared, I believe the success of every educational institution depends on its library as the availability of the right information at the right time and form is of utmost importance to users and an improvement of our library systems and access to information/knowledge will bring about social and human capital development. IFLA (2019) in her description of 3rd Roundtable of Ministers Responsible for Public Libraries in Africa held in Accra, Ghana from 28 – 30 October, aimed at improving information access and library systems corroborated the above assertion as it posits that Africa is faced with some of the world's most acute development challenges and needs to draw on all of its innovative potential. Information and equitable access to it IFLA declared will play a key role in achieving this,

Furtherance, libraries as social institutions for creativity, learning, research and leisure, the cardinal responsibility of librarians is to make available the right information and teach how to access them. As reported by Cunliffe-Jones, et al. (2021), media literacy, even in the broadest sense, was barely taught in six out of the seven countries they studied in June 2020 and no form of misinformation literacy was taught at all except in one province in South Africa. In the Library Schools, information literacy skills are taught and that places the librarians at a vantage point to assist other users. Therefore, below are some of the activities librarians do to curb information misuse..

Furthermore, libraries facilitate access to information thereby providing the means through which new knowledge is developed and made available to all. Knowledge is foundational to all spheres of life. An interrogation of this concept reveals that knowledge is critical for the growth of society and that knowledge is produced when information is absorbed, processed and internalized by individuals

(McCallum, 2013). Libraries, as critical providers of information have an important role to play in the creation of new knowledge. They are vital institutions for the creation, development and sustainability of knowledge societies. Information is a key input into the creation and maturation of knowledge, therefore, a significant criterion for a growing and healthy society is access to information. The library, as a major source for/conduit to information, serves a wide spectrum of information-seekers. Libraries are not only vital but also central to the facilitation of knowledge generation.. In the words of Ukoha (2013), Libraries remain portals of knowledge for everyone and they guarantee that whoever you are you can open the door to information, knowledge, learning and help.

To Vrane and Markovic (2015), libraries have always been educational, cultural and spiritual centres, places where people had access to relevant knowledge and information. These institutions invest greatly into the intellectual development of their users and contribute to the development of overall democracy of knowledge. They maintain that Librarians are intermediaries between library users and the knowledge whether in printed or digital form. According to Witek (2014), Librarians are not only knowledge creators but knowledge providers. He explains that historically, libraries and librarians are perceived as primary conduits for accessing knowledge as librarians provide knowledge to those who seek it through classification schema, bibliographic instruction, and purchase or license of scholarly materials.

Other roles highlighted to be played by libraries and librarians are: involving in citizens' enlightenment and engagement which can be achieved by the organizing seminars, symposium, and conferences through physical meetings, webinars, Zoom, Google classroom or Skype; Digital literacy and online safety training as well will help those who are not digital natives to approach online content with much understanding, .Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information as to knowing their previous activities,. Collaboration with professional fact checking organisation such as Africa Check, Dubawa and FactCheckHub, Collaboration with other institution, Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use and Checking and encouraging ethical use of information (Technopedia, 2018; Mavridis, 2019).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with the aim of collecting data on and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics features and facts about a given population. This type of study is only interested in describing certain variables like dependent and independent variables in relation to the population.

The sampled population for this study was 420 selected through purposive sampling technique among 4200 registered librarians in Nigeria from different types of libraries in Nigeria with the exception of the school librarians since no primary or secondary school in Nigeria can boast of a certified librarians. The sampled librarians were identified and selected with the help of Librarians'

Registration Council of Nigeria list of certified librarians in Nigeria as at 2022. The breakdown shows that academic libraries form 274 of the respondents; public libraries -111, special libraries -20 and national library-15 respondents

The primary instrument used in this study for data collection is the questionnaire. Apart from section 'A' of the instrument which dealt with demographic data the other aspect of the instrument was structured according to the modified Likert scale on four point rating scale. On this scale, the average mean cut off is 2.50, in which case, an item is accepted if it is 2.50 and above and rejected if it is below 2.50 hence the decision rule. The questionnaires were administered through email and returned 93%. The implication is that a total of 450 questionnaires were administered and only 420 were returned. Data collected were statistically analyzed using frequencies and percentile and presented in tables and charts.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: Who are those involved in information misuse?

Table 1: Creators of Information misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Traditional Media	188	44.76	112	26.67	70	16.67	50	11.9	Accepted
Politicians	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Public institutions	198	47.14	76	18.1	62	14.76	84	20	Accepted
Business leaders	120	28.57	160	38.1	60	14.29	80	19.05	Accepted
Traditional and religious leaders,	220	52.38	70	16.67	60	14.29	70	16.67	Accepted
Special interest groups	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Offline community networks	125	29.76	121	28.81	77	18.33	107	25.48	Accepted
ordinary social media users	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted

Table 1 is all about those who are creators of information misuse. The data reveal that the highest peddlers of information misuse are politicians, special interest groups and ordinary social media users with 100% or 420 respondents affirming to that, they were followed by traditional media with 300 or 71.43% affirmative responses while offline community networks took the rear with 246(58.57%) positive responses

Research question 2: What new media are used to peddle misinformation?

Table 2; New Media used for Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Radio	54	12.86	16	3.81	100	23.81	160	38.1	Rejected
Digital Television	80	19.05	20	4.76	220	52.38	100	23.81	Rejected
Twitter	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Instagram	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
LinkedIn	-	-	-	-	330	78.57	90	21.43	Rejected
Facebook Messenger	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
YouTube	290	69.05	55	13.1	30	7.14	45	10.71	Accepted
Whatsapp	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Snapchat	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Close Messaging Applications	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
blogs	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Google	23	5.48	77	18.33	98	23.33	222	52.86	Rejected
Yahoo	320	76.19	12	2.86	98	23.33	-	-	Accepted
TikTok	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted

Table 2 presents data collected in respect of the new media in use for information misuse or misinformation. The data revealed the entire 420 respondents representing 100% strongly agreed that Twitter; Instagram, Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Snapchat, Close Messaging Application, Blogs and TikTok are highly in use for information misuse while 345 of the respondents representing 82.14% agreed that YouTube is also highly used among other indicated new media.. Radios and digital televisions are also being used but to a lower extent.

Research question 3: What are the Consequences of information misuse?

Table 3: Consequences of Information Misuse

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Leads to erosion of trust among the people.	370	88.1	50	11.9	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public	411	97.86	09	2.14	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Can weaken democratic established institutions	84	20	202	48.1	54	12.86	80	19.05	Accepted
Can polarize the society	391	93.1	29	6.9	-	-	-	-	Accepted
It could also lead to suppression of minority groups in the country	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Accepted
Freedom of expression would be threatened with continued misinformation	320	76.19	50	11/9	10	2.38	40	9.52	Accepted
Can inhibit policy-making	120	28.57	111	26.43	90	21.43	99	23.57	Accepted

Table 5 contains data on the consequences of information misuse. The data collected reveal that 420 of the respondents or 100% strongly agreed or agreed that information misuse leads to suppression of minority groups in the country, leads to erosion of trust among the people and has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public, 370 or 88.1% strongly agreed or agreed that information misuse is a threat to freedom of expression and 286 or 68.1% agreed it can weaken democratic established institutions

Research question 4: What Roles are Librarians expected to play in the fight against information misuse?

Table 4: Roles of Libraries and Librarians

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Librarians should provide enlightenment to the teeming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation	420	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	Agreed
Librarian should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to									

identify potential risks associated with sharing personal information online.	420	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	Agreed
Assume the full position of information mediators	390	92.86	30	7.14	-	-	-	-	Agreed
Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information	420	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	Agreed
Collaboration with professional fact checking organisation	264	62.86	86	20.48	34	8.1	46	10.95	Agreed
. Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use	217	51.67	203	48.33	-	-	-	-	Agreed
Checking and encouraging ethical use of information	303	72.14	98	23.33	5	1.19	14	3.33	Agreed
Collaboration with other institutions	240	57.14	180	42.86	-	-	-	-	Agreed

The data in table 4 are the agreed perceived roles of libraries and librarians in the fight against information misuse. As shown in the table the entire 420 respondents or 100% strongly agreed that libraries and librarians should provide enlightenment to the teaming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation; should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to identify potential risks associated with sharing personal information online, Assume the full position of information mediators, and employ fact-checking techniques on the sources of information. The same 100% either strongly agreed or that libraries and librarians should work in collaboration with other institutions and get involved in packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The study also discovered as expressed in table 1 that the persons mostly involved in information misuse are politicians, ordinary social media users and special interest groups. The data also revealed at different proportion but above 60% positive responses that traditional and religious leaders, public institutions, business leaders, and traditional media among others are also involved in information misuse. This result affirms the findings of Cunliffe-Jones (2022) in his study of the creators of misinformation in Africa in which it was discovered that the creators include; traditional media and politicians, public institutions, business leaders, traditional and religious leaders, special interest groups, offline community networks and ordinary social media users.

The data as analyzed in table 2 reveals that new media such as Tweeter, Facebook Messenger; Instagram, Whatsapp, Snapchat, TikTok, Yahoo Messenger, Close Messaging Applications and Blogs are channels mostly used by those creators of misinformation or information misuse. Other media in use to certain degrees include; Google, digital televisions and radio. This finding further buttress the assertion that this powerful new technology makes the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplify falsehood peddled by states, populist politicians and dishonest corporate entities as they are shared by uncritical publics (Ireton & Posetti, 2018). This is also in line with Butcher (2019) who affirmed that online disinformation is deliberately false or misleading material, often masquerading as news content, which is designed to attract attention and exert influence through online channels.

Table 3 contains data that did reveal that the consequences of information misuse are enormous. According to the data collected, information misuse has so many negative effects on the society which include: it could also lead to suppression of minority groups in the country; has the capacity to manipulate the opinion of the public, can polarize the society, leads to erosion of trust among the people and can weaken democratic established institutions among others. This discovering is a affirmation of the view expressed that by misrepresenting reality with traces of truth, there is a distortion of entire collective imaginary and manipulation of public opinion which in turn leads to major problems politically, socially and economically (Satin & Pra, 2021)..The above view was also buttressed by Verizon (2021) and Reuter (2022) in their separate reports.

The data in table 4 highlighted the expected duties of librarians as information managers in the fight against information misuse. These duties among many others are; Libraries and librarians should provide enlightenment to the teaming unsuspecting Nigerians that are always falling prey to the web of misinformation and disinformation; Librarian should educate the public on how to identify legitimate sites and also to provide guidance on privacy protection, online security, and ability of the users to identify potential risks associated with sharing personal information online, Assume the full position of information mediators, Packaging accurate, reliable and factual information for future use and Collaboration with other institutions.

This result is in conformity with the assertion that Libraries as primary gateways to information are therefore important vehicles for the acquisition of knowledge. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities and socio-economic groups regardless of their information/knowledge needs (Akintunde, 2004; IFLA, 2019; Onwubiko, 2020). It is also in tandem with the views expressed by Technopedia (2018) and Mavridis (2019) that libraries and librarians should be involved in citizens' enlightenment and engagement through the organizations of seminars, symposium, and conferences, physical meetings, webinars,

Zoom, Google classroom or Skype and also conduct digital literacy and online safety training through which those who are not digital natives are can be helped to approach online content with much understanding, .As well as applying Fact-checking techniques on the sources of information as to knowing their previous activities and collaborating with professional fact checking organisation such as Africa Check, Dubawa and FactCheckHub.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The outcome of this study has actually shown that information misuse which may be in the form of misinformation, mal-information, propaganda, fake new, rumor and hoax, manipulated media or conspiracy theories are mostly created by politicians, those in government, traditional leaders, business leaders, individual users of social media among others using various new media for propagation. Generally, the outcome of this study has exposed the fact that information misuse is a hydra-headed monster which if not checked can sink our society. While the new media stands as a double edge sword with the first edge representing initial intention of enhancement of access to information and easy to access a wide range of information on practically every topic, from everyday issues to academic research. Besides, people can find information online regardless of their location and often for free, meaning new media is a very valuable resource and the second the awkward application in which the new media technology has made the manipulation and fabrication of content simple and social networks dramatically amplifying falsehood. To this end, it was discovered that librarians have prominent roles to play in the fight against this anti-social act (see table 4) The implication is that librarians are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the right information goes out and wrong ones countered. The people need to know how to fact-check information before sharing. People should be enlightened on the appropriate channels to access information, because even the conventional information channels are faced with menace of misinformation and disinformation. Libraries as credible and reputable social institutions whose contents are not in doubt should therefore champion the course of dispelling information misuse in our society. Going by the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. In the first instance, Librarians should occupy the drivers' seats as information mediators and directors with a view to winning public confidence through the provision and dissemination of accurate and reliable information.
2. Public libraries which is so to speak the people's universities should be built in every part of a country to enable the citizens have access to the right information always with each installed with 'user monitoring solution'. One of the best ways to detect and prevent data misuse is to see exactly what happens after data is accessed. A dedicated user monitoring solution allows you to easily see what has happened with data when it was used, how and by whom.
3. Libraries' management should as a matter of necessity train every staff on cyber and data security as a general corporate policy. A well-thought-out policy is a reliable source of information about in-house procedures and standards.
4. Library schools should set up educational courses on data security. A generic course on cyber-security is always useful to remind staff not to share their credentials, inform them about new phishing methods, among others. Librarians should be well informed on why it's important to take care of sensitive data and what consequences data misuse will have not only for the library and themselves but also for the society at large. This to say, that library staffs should be up to speed with technology and use their social media handles to disseminate reliable information and to also counter misused information in the media.
5. Information misuse as a crime against the society should be considered a serious offence, there countries should enact stringent laws that will make offenders/perpetrators pay dearly for it as to serve as deterrent to others who may be having the intention to indulge in such act.
6. New media, of all sorts should be regulated by the state. Since all views, opinions and content can be freely expressed and accessed on the internet; measures should be taken to combat potentially harmful content e.g. homophobic, racist and terrorism-inciting comments and websites. To breathe easy, libraries should not only secure all their data at rest and in transit but also wisely configure notifications and provide courses to support their staff members. This implies that Social media website owners should properly monitor the kinds of information being circulated to the public and should be ready to take down any information that is capable of causing problem in the society.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, A., and Sodiq, O. 2023,. How Presidential Candidates Pay Influencers to Peddle Fake News on Social Media, by CDD report. www.guardian.ng.
- Akintunde, S.A, 2004, Libraries as Tool for ICT Development in a Paper Presented at the National Library Association 42nd National Conference and Annual General Meeting. Akure, Nigeria: June, 20 - 25.

- Andrew, K., 2007, *The Cult of the amateur: How today's Internet is Killing our Culture*, California, USA: Doubleday/Currency
- Baines, D. and Elliott, R.J.R, 2020, *Defining Misinformation, Disinformation and Mal-Information: An Urgent Need for Clarity During the Covid-19 Infodemic*. Discussion Papers, 20-26.
- Butcher, P., 2019, *Disinformation and Democracy: The Home Front in the Information War*. European Politics and Institutions Programme. European Policy Centre.
- Chavali, S., 2018, 5 Examples of Insider Threat-Caused Breaches that Illustrate the Scope of the Problem. Retrieved from <https://www.proofpoint.com/us/blog/insider-threat-management/5-examples-insider-threat-caused-breaches-illustrate-scope-problem>
- Chavis, J.C., 2023, What is New Media Technology? Retrieved from <https://www.easytechjunkie.com/what-is-new-media-technology.htm>
- Colomina, C., Margalef, H.R., and Youngs, R., 2021, *The Impact of Disinformation on Democratic Processes and Human Rights in the World*. Policy Department, Directorate- General for External Policies, European Union.
- Cornford, J and Robins, K., 1999, cited in Study Smarter (2023) *New Media: Definition, Examples & Disadvantages*. Retrieved from <https://www.studysmarter.us/explanations/social-studies/the-media/new-media/>
- Cunliffe-Jones, P. et al., 2021. *Misinformation Policy in Sub-Saharan Africa: From Laws and Regulations to Medical Literacy*. London: University of Westminster Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16997/book53>.
- Curran, J., 2002, *Media and Power*. London: Routledge
- Curran, J. and Seaton, J. 2003. *Power without Responsibility: The Press, Broadcasting, and New Media in Britain*. London: Routledge
- deWatteville, A. and Gilbert, L. , 2000. *Advanced Information and Communication Technology*. Oxford: Heinemann Educational Publishers
- Ekran System 2023, 4 Ways to Detect and Prevent Misuse Data. Retrieved from <https://www.ekransystem.com/en/blog/4-ways-detect-and-prevent-misuse-data>
- Friedman, L.W and Friedman, H.H. 2008. *The New Media Technologies: Overview and Research Framework*. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2-29. DOI: 10.2139/ssm.1116771.
- Harrison, K. and Boyd, T., 2018, *Democracy: Understanding Political Ideas and Movements*. Retrieved from: <http://www.manchesteropenhive.com>
- Hill, K.A. and Hughes, J. E., 1998, *Cyber-politics: Citizen Activism in the Age of the Internet*. München. Germany: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers
- International Crisis Group, 2023, *Mitigating Risk of Violence in Nigeria's 2023 Elections*. Africa Report: 1050 Brussels, Belgium
- IFLA., 2019, *Description. 3rd Roundtable of Ministers Responsible for Public Libraries in Africa*. Accra, Ghana; 28 – 30 October. <http://www.ifla.org/node/92608>
- Ireton, J., and Posetti, C., 2018, *Journalism, Fake news and Misinformation: Handbook for Journalism Education and Training*. UNESCO

- Jerit, J., and Zhao, Y. 2020, Political Misinformation. Annual Review of Political Science. Department of Political Science, Stony Brook University: New York, USA. Retrieved From: www.annualreviews.org
- Johns, K. , 2019, Online Disinformation and Political Discourse: Applying a Human Rights Framework. International Law Program, 1-64.
- Lewis, R., and Marwick, A., 2017, Taking the Red Pill: Ideological Motivations for Spreading Online Disinformation, in Understanding and Addressing the Disinformation Ecosystem, Annenberg School for Communication, December, 2017.
- Mavridis, G., 2019, Fake News and Social Media: How Greek Users Identify and Curb Misinformation Online. Malmö University, Faculty of Culture and Society.
- Nai, L and Kirkup, G., 2007, Gender and Cultural Differences in Internet use: A Study of China and the UK. Computers & Education 48, 301–317
- Nwajiuba, C., 2019, Libraries on the African Development Agenda- Progress made. 3rd Ministerial Roundtable on Information Access with Regard to the African Union Agenda 2063 & the Charter for African Cultural Renaissance, Accra, Ghana. 28 -30 October. www.fb.com/ChukwuemekaNwajiuba
- Onwubiko, E.C., 2016, Library Plus. Abakaliki, Nigeria: Good Tiding Press
- Onwubiko, E, C., 2020, An Empirical Study of Librarians and Libraries as Drivers of Access to Knowledge in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies 5(5), 43-59
- New Media Institute, n.d , What is new media? Retrieved from <http://nmi.cool/about/>
- Reuter, 2022,. Client data leaked to media. Retrieved from <http://www.reuter.com/business/finance/credit-suisse-denies-wrongdoing-after-client-data-leaked-media-2022-02-20>
- Santin, J.R. and Pra, M.D. 2021. Fake news, Misinformation and Civil and Political Fundamental Rights. International Journal of Law and Public Administration, 4(1), 12-20.
- Santos-D'amorim, K., and Miranda, M.K.F. , (2021) , Misinformation, Disinformation, and Malinformation: Clarifying the Definitions and Examples in Disinformation Times. Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5007/1518-2924.2021.e76900>
- Southern New Hampshire University, 2023, What are Examples of New Media? <https://www.snhu.edu/about-us/newsroom/liberal-arts/what-is-new-media>
- Technopedia, 2018, What is a Filter Bubble? - Definition from Technopedia. [Online] Available at: <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/28556/filterbubble> [Accessed 15 February 2023].
- Ukoha O. I., 2013, Driving Access to Knowledge: Role of Libraries in Nigeria| PCF 7, Dec 2-6, Abuja Nigeria
- U.S. Ministry of Justice, 2020, Chinese Citizen Convicted. Retrieved from <http://www.Justice.gov/opa/pr/chines-citizen-convicted-economic-espionage-theft-trade-secrets-and-conspiracy>
- Varizon 2021. Data Breach Investigation Reports. Retrieved from <http://www.verizon.com/business/resources/reports/dbir>
- Vrane, A., and Markovic, L., 2015, Librarians as information and knowledge managers. Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries (QQML), 4: 903 - 912

Wardle, C and Derakhshan, H., 2017, Information Disorder: Towards an Interdisciplinary Framework for Research and Policy-making. Council of Europe. Retrieved from <https://rm.coe.int/information-order-toward-an-interdisciplinary-framework-for-research/16>.

Witek, D., 2014, Meta Literacy. <http://www.donnawitek.com/metaliteracy>

Womboh, B.S.H., and Abba, T. , 2008, The State of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigerian University Libraries: The experience of Ibrahim Babangida Library, Federal University of Technology, Yola. Library Philosophy and Practice. Retrieved from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP/womboh.htm>